

Mixed Ligand Complexes Containing Bidentate Tertiary and Primary Amines

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The binary compounds $[M(A)(H_2O)_4]SO_4$, where $M = Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II)$; $A =$ dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline were isolated. From these binary compounds ternary compounds $[M(A)(L)(H_2O)_2]SO_4$, where $M = Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II)$; $A =$ dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline and $L =$ ethylenediamine(en) or propylenediamine(pn). The ternary compounds contain two water molecules in the coordination sphere. The structures were confirmed by magnetic, visible spectral, reflectance spectral and IR spectral studies.

MIXED ligand complexes of the type $[MAL]$, where $M = Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II)$ and $Cd(II)$; $A =$ dipyridyl(dipy) or *o*-phenanthroline (*o*-phen) and $L =$ ethylenediamine(en) or propylenediamine(pn) have been studied earlier in solution¹. The present investigation gives an account of the isolation of the compounds and their characterisation. Mixed ligand complexes containing dipyridyl and other ligands have been reported earlier²⁻⁵. The complexes $[MLX_2]$, where $M = Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(III), Ni(II), Cu(II)$; $L =$ dipy, *o*-phen; $X = Cl', Br'$ have been reported recently⁶. In the present investigation complex $[M(dipy)(H_2O)_4]SO_4$ has been first prepared and then two water molecules have been replaced by the diamine.

The compounds $[M(A)(H_2O)_4]SO_4$, where $M = Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II)$; $A =$ dipy or *o*-phen were prepared as follows :

To 10 ml of 1M aqueous metal sulphate solution was added 10 ml of 1M alcoholic dipy. or *o*-phen, solution with stirring. The mixture was refluxed for half an hour and alcohol was added to precipitate out the solid. The precipitates were filtered and washed with alcohol+water (1 : 1) mixture. They were dried in the oven at 80°. The analysis of the compounds corresponds to the composition $[M(A)(H_2O)_4]SO_4$ where $M = Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II)$; $A =$ dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline. In case of $Cu(II)$ however, the dimeric complex is known to be formed when dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline is added to the metal salt solution². $Zn(II)$ and $Cd(II)$ complexes are white in colour. $Ni(II)$ complexes have green colour as shown in the Table 2.

To 5 ml of 1M aqueous solution of the above solids was added 5 ml of 1M aqueous solution of en or pn with constant stirring. The mixture was concentrated to reduce the volume. To this mixture, alcohol was added, to precipitate out the solid. The precipitates were washed with alcohol+water (1 : 2) mixture. They were dried at 80° in the oven.

The analysis of the compounds corresponds to the composition $[M(A)(en)(H_2O)_2]SO_4$ or $[M(A)(pn)(H_2O)_2]SO_4$, where $M = Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II)$; except in case of $[Cd(dipy)(L)(H_2O)_2]SO_4$ ($L = en$ or pn) where the analysis does not agree with the expected values. $Cu(II)$ and $Ni(II)$ complexes are coloured as shown in the Table 2.

The compounds were analysed for metal, nitrogen and sulphate contents. In two cases carbon and hydrogen have also been estimated. The results have been presented in the table.

The values of equivalent conductance were determined for 0.01N and 0.0005N (infinite dilution) aqueous solutions using Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge of the type 101/01A.

The value of the equivalent conductance at 0.01N for all complexes was ~ 110 . The ratio of equivalent conductance at 0.01M and infinite dilution is ~ 0.70 . This shows that all complexes are bivalent-bivalent electrolytes⁷. The conductivity measurements were repeated after a gap of 1 hr for 6 hr. The values remain constant indicating that the compounds do not decompose in water.

The binary compounds contain four water molecules in the coordination sphere. These water molecules are lost at temperature beyond 120°, indicating that they are not water of crystallisation but are coordinated water. This was further confirmed by magnetic and spectral studies.

The magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes $[Ni(dipy)(H_2O)_4]^{+2}$ and $[Ni(o\text{-phen})(H_2O)_4]^{+2}$ were determined by Gouy's method. Ni^{2+} complexes were observed to be paramagnetic with a magnetic moment ~ 3.2 B.M. corresponding to two unpaired electrons. This indicates that the compounds have distorted octahedral structure, the water molecules being in coordination sphere.

The absorption spectra of the binary $Ni(II)$ compounds were studied in aqueous solution in the

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND CONDUCTANCE VALUES OF THE COMPOUNDS

Name of the complex	Analytical data %						Equi. Cond. ohms ⁻¹ cm ²	Conduc- tance ratio
	Expected			Observed				
	Ni	N	SO ₄	Ni	N	SO ₄		
[Ni(dipy)(H ₂ O) ₄]SO ₄	15.33	7.31	25.07	15.50	7.02	25.10	107	0.69
[Ni(dipy)(en)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	14.42	13.76	23.58	14.60	13.95	23.62	101	0.71
[Ni(dipy)(pn)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	13.94	13.30	22.80	14.24	13.00	22.92	105	0.73
[Ni(o-phen)(H ₂ O) ₄]SO ₄	13.81	6.58	22.59	13.65	6.34	22.66	101	0.68
[Ni(o-phen)(en)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	13.07	12.47	21.38	13.12	12.52	21.60	98	0.65
[Ni(o-phen)(pn)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	12.67	12.09	20.73	12.90	12.32	21.00	100	0.66
[Cu(dipy)(en)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	15.42	13.59	23.30	15.60	13.72	23.50	107	0.75
[Cu(dipy)(pn)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	14.92	13.15	22.54	15.00	13.25	22.80	104	0.72
[Cu(o-phen)(en)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	14.00	12.34	21.15	14.20	12.50	21.40	101	0.73
[Cu(o-phen)(pn)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	13.58	11.97	20.52	13.62	11.82	20.42	97	0.76
[Zn(dipy)(H ₂ O) ₄]SO ₄	16.78	7.18	24.64	16.50	7.45	24.35	101	0.70
[Zn(dipy)(en)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	15.70	13.53	23.20	15.62	13.60	23.30	103	0.66
[Zn(dipy)(pn)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	15.28	13.09	22.44	15.44	13.36	22.70	105	0.65
[Zn(o-phen)(H ₂ O) ₄]SO ₄	15.16	6.49	22.26	15.00	6.60	22.00	102	0.63
[Zn(o-phen)(en)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	14.35	12.29	21.08	14.60	12.45	21.20	99	0.72
[Zn(o-phen)(pn)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	13.92	11.92	20.43	13.75	11.60	20.21	100	0.71
[Cd(dipy)(H ₂ O) ₄]SO ₄	25.74	6.41	21.99	26.00	6.25	22.10	109	0.69
[Cd(o-phen)(H ₂ O) ₄]SO ₄	23.48	5.84	20.05	23.64	5.62	20.30	111	0.68
[Cd(o-phen)(en)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	22.36	11.14	19.09	22.50	11.32	19.40	113	0.65
[Cd(o-phen)(pn)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	21.75	10.83	18.57	21.91	11.00	18.20	110	0.63
		Expected			Observed			
		C	H		C	H		
[Ni(dipy)(H ₂ O) ₄]SO ₄		31.35	4.18		31.22	4.20		
[Ni(dipy)(en)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄		35.38	4.91		35.42	5.00		

TABLE 2—COLOUR, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS OF THE COMPOUNDS

Name of the complex	Colour	Electronic spectral Bands				Magnetic moments in B.M.
		λ	λ	ϵ	ϵ	
[Ni(dipy)(H ₂ O) ₄]SO ₄	Bluish green	580	920	3.3	4.6	3.32
[Ni(dipy)(en)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	Grey	590	920	5.2	6.2	3.28
[Ni(dipy)(pn)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	Grey	570	920	5.0	6.5	3.19
[Ni(o-phen)(H ₂ O) ₄]SO ₄	Green	600	940	2.8	3.8	3.22
[Ni(o-phen)(en)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	Grey	570	920	5.8	6.4	3.15
[Ni(o-phen)(pn)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	Grey	580	900	5.5	6.6	3.20
[Cu(dipy)(en)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	Blue	560	—	124	—	1.80
[Cu(dipy)(pn)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	Blue	570	—	63	—	1.78
[Cu(o-phen)(en)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	Blue	580	—	61	—	1.82
[Cu(o-phen)(pn)(H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄	Blue	570	—	53	—	1.76

region 400–1000 nm using DU2 Beckman Spectrophotometer at room temperature (30°). The optical density was plotted against wavelength. Ni(II) complexes show two bands, one at 570 nm and other at 940 nm corresponding to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ transitions. The third transition ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ occurs in the U.V. region. The extinction coefficients for the bands are also low. This shows that the spectra of binary compounds correspond

to distorted octahedral structures⁸. In aqueous solution, however, solvent molecules may get coordinated at 5th and 6th positions in a square planar structure, thus making it octahedral. Therefore, the reflectance spectra of two Ni(II) compounds were also obtained in the range 400–1000 nm in LiF medium in solid state. The bands are obtained at the same position as in aqueous solution confirming the octahedral structure of the Ni(II) complexes.

On addition of ethylenediamine or propylenediamine following reaction takes place

The mixed ligand complexes are also paramagnetic, the values of magnetic moment being ~ 3.2 B.M. for Ni(II) complexes and ~ 1.7 B.M. for Cu(II) complexes. The absorption spectra of Ni(II) compounds in solution are of same nature as in the binary complexes. The reflectance spectra of compound II in Table 2 was obtained in LiF medium, in solid state. The bands are obtained at the same position as in aqueous solution. This shows that the Ni(II) complexes have distorted octahedral structure. In case of Cu(II) compounds one broad band is obtained at ~ 575 nm. This corresponds to combination of ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transition⁹. in agreement with distorted octahedral structure. Thus the two water molecules in the mixed complexes must be in the coordination sphere.

The infrared spectra of the complexes have been obtained in the range $4000-600$ cm^{-1} in nujol. All the spectra show broad band at 3400 cm^{-1} due to O-H stretching indicating the presence of water molecule in the structure. In all the complexes aliphatic and aromatic C-H stretching bands are observed. In the ethylenediamine and propylenediamine complexes the broad band due to O-H

spread upto 3300 cm^{-1} indicating the combination of N-H stretching with the O-H stretching vibration. The other bands are obtained as expected. The band at 770 cm^{-1} may correspond to $\bar{H}-OH$ out of plane bending, indicating the presence of coordinated water molecule in the complexes. This cannot however, be said conclusively, because other vibrations of the dipyridyl molecule may occur in this region.

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